

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ВЫСШЕЙ ШКОЛЕ**Пиримжаров М.**

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В статье рассматривается в настоящее время в системе высшего образования создаются традиции формирования студентов в качестве активного и творческого участника учебного процесса. Это объясняется потребностью современного общества в инициативных, грамотных, самостоятельно получающих и использующих новую информацию, постоянно повышающих свою профессиональную квалификацию специалистах.

Учебный процесс высшей школы направлен на всестороннюю подготовку специалистов, и требует осуществления систематической работы по развитию и управлению познавательной деятельностью студентов в условиях овладения ими определенными профессиональными знаниями, умениями и навыками. Образование в высшей школе должно быть подчинено овладению большим объемом информации, формированию эффективного, творческого мышления, развитию интеллектуального потенциала личности, логический анализ и всестороннюю обработку информации.

Одним из важных условий подготовки специалистов, согласно современным требованиям, является активизация самостоятельной учебной деятельности студентов.

Особое внимание при этом уделяется формированию таких качеств у специалистов, как самостоятельность, творчество (креативность), предприимчивость, активность.

В системе высшего образования внимание уделялось самообразованию. Безупречным специалистом может быть только студент, обученный самостоятельно осваивать учебный материал, расширять и укреплять объем его научной информации.

Abstract

The article discusses the traditions of forming students as an active and creative participant in the educational process are currently being created in the higher education system. This is explained by the need of modern society for proactive, literate, independently receiving and using new information, constantly improving their professional

qualifications.

The educational process of higher education is aimed at comprehensive training of specialists, and requires systematic work on the development and management of cognitive activity of students in the conditions of mastering certain professional knowledge, skills and abilities. Education in higher education should be subordinated to mastering a large amount of information, the formation of effective, creative thinking, the development of the intellectual potential of the individual, logical analysis and comprehensive processing of information.

One of the important conditions for training specialists, according to modern requirements, is the activation of independent educational activities of students.

Special attention is paid to the formation of such qualities among specialists as independence, creativity (creativity), entrepreneurship, activity.

In the higher education system, attention was paid to self-education. An impeccable specialist can only be a student who is trained to master the educational material independently, expand and strengthen the volume of his scientific information.

Ключевые слова: высшего образования, самостоятельной образования, технология, критерия, аудитория, анализ, содержания, организация.

Keywords: higher education, independent education, technology, criteria, audience, analysis, content, organization.

Introduction

Independent education is a part of the study time allocated to an academic subject, and independent assimilation by students of the material intended for it is provided. The volume of independent education is 15-20 percent of the study time allocated to the discipline in the bachelor's degree, and 40-45 percent in the master's degree. The normative documents on the reform of the higher education system indicate that independent education is an extracurricular form of the educational process and is organized in the form of theoretical and practical tasks (homework, abstract, graphic assignment, term paper or part of it, etc.) according to the curriculum developed by professors-teachers. In the standard curricula of academic disciplines published in 2009, independent education is defined as "the assimilation of materials not included in the work program". The form of independent education should be clearly indicated in the working curriculum of the discipline. For independent education is one of the main factors that have a direct impact on the quality of students' knowledge. At the meeting of the Board of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education on December 24, 2009, the issue of the problems of the formation of independent learning, the skills of independent assimilation of knowledge by students was considered. It was decided that professors-teachers in their individual work plans in the section "Methodical work" included the development in the 2008-2009 academic year of methodological manuals and guidelines aimed at forming students' ability to self-study and assimilation of knowledge (collections of situational tasks, individual assignments, handouts, etc.).

Research and methods

Special attention in the new curricula developed on the basis of state standards of higher education is paid to the issue of self-education of students. Analysis, scientific and theoretical justification, methodological development of the system of methods and means of self-education of students.

- transfer the studied material;
- expand the amount of knowledge of the student;
- to form practical skills and abilities of the trainee;
- manage the teacher's learning activities and the cognitive activity of the student;

- to stimulate a scientific approach to the creation of new material for independent education.

The materials of independent education used in the system of independent education assume various tasks. Among them can be listed: informational, cognitive, educational, intellectual, developmental, motivational, stimulating, innovative and other tasks, as well as self-determination, management and control [1, -p 5].

Discussion

In the curricula developed on the basis of state standards of higher education, special attention is paid to the independent education of students. When organizing students' independent education, it is important to optimally allocate students' time budget. Here, the department is responsible for organizational and control work, which should coordinate independent work taking into account the student's time budget. Teachers are responsible for the systematic and meaningful nature of this work. Criteria for monitoring and evaluating the level of development of skills and abilities of independent work of students are determined based on the specifics of the subject. The analysis of the budget of time allocated for independent education shows its monotony, i.e. the specific features of each discipline are not taken into account. As you know, determining the ratio (proportion) of study hours allocated for classroom and extracurricular work is one of the main conditions for improving the educational process. To date, no consensus has been reached on this issue. The main part of specialists, based on the weekly budget of the student's study time of 54 hours, classroom classes of 36 hours, believes that the ratio of time for classroom and extracurricular independent education should be 1: 0.5, and the daytime for independent education should not exceed 3 hours.

An analysis of the curricula and programs developed in recent years shows that in the updated versions of the curricula of some areas of education, "independent education" is mistakenly identified with "independent work". Independent work is only one form of independent education. Independent education is the expansion of the volume of scientific knowledge gained in the classroom in the process of reading additional literature, completing term papers (projects), solving metric and situational tasks, etc. [2, -p 186]

Independent education in the higher education system is a purposeful educational activity of students for the independent assimilation of knowledge, which is directed and managed by a teacher (a topic for independent study and literature are recommended, tasks for independent work are given, teaching aids are recommended, consultations are organized and implementation is monitored) [3, -p 75-77].

The main goal of independent education is to increase the independence and activity of students, develop thinking, strengthen the implementation of acquired knowledge based on the final stage of the National Training Program. The improvement of a modern specialist's knowledge and life experience depends on the level of formation of his personal qualities. Independent work is of particular importance for the formation of such qualities. The main task of independent work is to consolidate the knowledge and skills acquired in classroom classes, the assimilation of new ones and the formation of creative work skills [4, -p. 5].

According to V.A.Slastenin, independent education is such an activity of a student to acquire knowledge, where consistent thinking, a sequence of mental and practical operations, and actions depend on himself [5, -p. 48].

Independent education is a set of independent works based on a special systematic approach to education, writes A.K.Bushlya [6, -p. 16].

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences N.A.Muslimov emphasizes that independent education (autodidactics) means the organization, consistent with the subjective goals of the educational process, of independent and autonomous activities for the assimilation of knowledge, the development of ideas, the formation of concepts, skills and abilities. Autonomy in the independent assimilation of knowledge is the ability to define, choose goals, principles, content, methods and means of learning, the ability to implement them without difficulty and outside help. Independence is manifested in special qualities, abilities, activity, concentration of attention, mobilization of all their forces to achieve the goal [7, -p. 46].

As important features, the author shows the following: autonomy is the ability to define, choose goals, principles, content, methods and means of teaching, the ability to implement them without difficulty and outside help. Autonomy is an independent acquisition of knowledge, it can be considered as problem-based learning, work based on a research method.

The technology of self-assimilation of knowledge and the reasons for self-acquisition of knowledge are interrelated: uncertainty in achieving a specific result more than any other reason distances the student from self-assimilation of knowledge [8, -p.34].

Independent education makes serious demands on the student. Unlike the educational process, where the result of the joint activity of the teacher and the student is known in advance, with the independent assimilation of knowledge, the subject must receive unforeseen and unplanned results in advance, i.e. a specific amount of knowledge, skills and abilities. This process, which

consists in the independent performance of an educational task with the participation of a teacher to one degree or another, is an important link in improving the personality of students [9, -p 146].

The educational material used in individual training and independent education (materials for independent education) forms the basis of mutual communication between the teacher and the student. The development and implementation of independent education materials into pedagogical practice is an important pedagogical problem.

The content of independent education forms the basis of the system of independent education of students. The content of independent education is the material of independent education, the activity of the educator and the trainee. At the same time, the main role is played by the communication between the teacher and the student [10, -p 77-84].

The main means of independent education are the materials of independent education. They, being a consistently connected system, differ from textbooks, teaching aids and lecture texts. They contain specific and meaningful methodological guidelines, a control unit for the cognitive activity of the student, criteria for independent learning in the process of professional training, psychological and pedagogical recommendations for self-orientation to independent learning, self-control, self-expression and self-esteem. The material for independent education is given in the form of recommendations on the use of teaching aids, lecture texts, computer programs, audio and video materials, existing traditional textbooks, and other sources of information [11, -p. 10].

With the development of the system of independent education, the role of educational (didactic) materials is changing [12, -p 32].

The development of independent education materials is usually carried out by specialists of a higher educational institution, i.e. professors-teachers experienced in the field of this discipline.

Under these conditions, the content of teachers' activities changes. Their methodological function is of great importance here. The system of independent education provides very wide opportunities. In the course of their cognitive activity, students, along with the educational material received from teachers, use additional information. This information appears to them as a fruit of self-awareness and independent education. Despite the great importance of the educational material sent by the teacher, the information acquired by the student in the process of self-awareness is more productive [13, -p 172].

The content of independent education is much broader than the content of education. A student in the process of independent education has the right to choose the content of education. It reflects the goals and objectives of the student in mastering certain knowledge and skills.

The material of independent education has various didactic possibilities, namely:

increases (strengthens) the knowledge, skills and abilities of the learner;

activates the main ideas, concepts, processes related to the studied processes [14, -p 11].

The materials of independent education are classified according to several criteria:

1. By the nature of the educational material: knowledge and information obtained from textbooks, educational and methodological manuals; additional material; standard texts of lectures, etc.

2. According to the volume of educational information: the full volume of the studied questions, information on the subject of the discipline. Information technology-related material.

3. By term of use: handout for one-time use; material used in the classroom repeatedly [15, -p 192]

The material of independent education, communication between students and the teacher are the leading components in the process of independent education. The degree of interaction of these two components contributes to the equation of models of open education.

This activity will be effective under the following circumstances. The student's activity will be effective if he can independently use educational and training materials, distinguish and analyze them. At the same time the following skills of the trainee are important:

- work with scientific documentation, highlighting the uniqueness in its content, classification of the studied phenomena and factors;

- analysis of the educational material, highlighting the leading ideas and their argumentation (justification);

- systematization of educational material, identification of the main components, determination of pronounced connections between them, their didactic capabilities;

- regulation (ordering) of the process of using the material of independent education, their replenishment and updating.

It should be taken into account the fact that many students have not previously faced the problem of independent work, with the material of independent education. The materials of independent education, unlike textbooks, educational and methodological manuals, are complex by the nature of the structure. As practice shows, many trainees in the learning process cannot objectively assess their skills in working with material for independent education. This assessment is always personal (subjective). A serious problem arises – how to ensure the objectivity of this process. In our opinion, there is a solution to this problem – it is necessary to develop, define, justify and apply criteria for assessing students' skills with material for independent education. Certain criteria should be dynamic and flexible. Each student chooses criteria in accordance with their readiness for self-assessment, organization and correction of their activities.

The criteria for assessing the level of mastery of students' skills of independent work with the material of independent education look like this: the highest level – the student has mastered the educational information transmitted in lectures and practical classes on the subject, is inclined to consolidate and expand the scope of this information. Familiar with the electronic textbook and other literature available in the center of

information and resources of the educational institution, has the skills to draw the necessary material from them and perform independent work correctly and in full; high level – the student has mastered the educational information transmitted in lectures and practical classes on the subject, but is indifferent to the consolidation and expansion of this information, is familiar with the literature available in the information and resources center of the educational institution, sometimes devotes time to this; intermediate level - the student partially possesses the skills of independent work with the material for independent education, i.e. is not familiar with the electronic literature available in the center of information and resources of the educational institution, audio, video materials, materials, partially possesses the knowledge and skills to perform independent work.

Conclusion

1. When training competitive specialists in the conditions of modern automated production, the only condition for organizing the educational process at the level of modern requirements is the activation of independent educational activities of students.

2. In the course of the study, a system of self-education was created. These are materials for self-education, self-education (additional literature, audio - video materials, computer programs, multimedia tools and Internet materials).

3. The main components of self-education are the content of education, the materials of self-education, the relationship between the teacher and the student. In the course of the study, a system of self-education of students was developed.

4. Independent education is a factor of increasing the level of training of future specialists, the effective organization of which requires a model approach to the development of material for independent education. In the course of the research, a modular method of preparing independent educational material was developed.

5. The material for self-education is the main link of the system of self-education, the completeness and practicality of which largely determines the effectiveness of the educational process, which was confirmed in the course of the study.

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